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Seasonal outbreak of *Thrips tabaci* on different cotton cultivars in relation to abiotic factors and different sowing times

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Abstract

Nowadays approximately 20 thrips species have been reported to infest cotton internationally causing considerable yield losses. Monitoring thrips is hard as they are about minute and are mysterious feeders, which build thrips not easy to manage by chemical. The present investigations were designed to test out the seasonal outbreak of thrips individuals on two cotton varieties and effect of ecological components markedly temperature, humidity and rainfall on it. The impact of different sowing dates was also intentional. The results indicated that thrips population was maximum (11.83/leaf) found on Cyto-179 and (8.22/leaf) on IUB-2013. In the first sown cotton, the peak activity of thrips was during the second week of August while for second planting time it was first week of August. The results from correlation analysis showed the positive association was found between the thrips abundance and temperature. While the analysis showed unconstructive correlation of relative humidity and rainfall with thrips abundance. Both cotton cultivars proved extra vulnerable to the thrips hit. A biotic factors played momentous role in the growth along with surveillance of this pest. So, by managing the agronomic factors, e.g. sowing time, cotton yield could be enhanced by reducing the infestation of thrips.

Keywords: *Thrips tabaci*, Seasonal outbreak, Abiotic factors, Sowing times and pest management, Cotton cultivars

1. Introduction

The complete place that is known for Pakistan is 796,095 km², around twenty to million are developed and 8.3 million are non-developed soil. Around the globe Pakistan is among the foremost makers of cotton, wheat, sugarcane, rice, dates, mango and oranges. Our chief crops (includes cotton, wheat, sugar cane and rice) contribute 6.5% but trivial crops 2.3% of the nation's GDP. Pakistan's agriculture is based on chief crops which report for approximately 24% of the worth supplementary to generally agriculture and 4.67% of the GDP (Azam and Shafique, 2017).

Cotton, *Gossypiumhirsutum* isn't only the most significant material yarn on worldwide basis, anyway is likewise the primary abroad exchange worker underdeveloped nations (Morris, 1990). It gives the superb supply of eatable oil and typical filament (Aslam *et al.*, 2004). The cotton harvest have high importance with twin reason as it gives strand along oil suitable for eating (Mallah *et al.*, 1997). In Pakistan normal cotton production is about five hundred and seventy Kilogram per Hectare. It is lesser in comparison with the yield of other saleable cotton growers (Bakhsh, 2005), for the reason that the major difficulty in cotton growing is the attack of insect pests (Naqvi, 1976). Developing countries including Pakistan have low yield production of seed cotton

as compared to other technologically advanced countries like USA, Australia and China etc. Therefore, high yield of cotton is necessary on consecutive basis (USDA, 2010). Cotton and its relative products are chief exported materials in Pakistan to many countries of the world including USA. From which the significance of seed cotton for countries economy and growers is shown (Rehman, 2002).

In the world over thirteen hundred and twenty six type of pests that mainly insects found as basis of infestation in cotton (Atwal, 2002), whereas 162 different types of insect and mite pests in sub-continent (Manjunath, 2004). The cotton crop is attacked by ninety six different types of insect pests and mite species during its growth period. These insects and other pests normally observed to nourish on fiber crop in Pakistan (Younas *et al.*, 1980). In Pakistan, the key pests of cotton crop had sucking type of mouth parts are thrips, jassid, whitefly and they cause considerable loss in cotton production (Amjad and Aheer, 2007; Aslam *et al.*, 2004). Insects with sucking type of mouth parts became primary pests of cotton crop from the time transgenic cotton (Bt cotton) commercialized in the world especially in Pakistan (Holt *et al.*, 2006). In India, Japan, Trinidad, Puerto Rico, Australia and Europe; Thrips, *Thrips tabaci* (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) have been found as major cotton pest (Ananthakrishnan, 1984). Thrips generally attack on the cotton crop during the whole growing season. But they cause a lot of economic damage to the crop at sapling period (Dunham and Clark 1937; Reay-Jones *et al.*, 2017). Overwintering stage of this pest is normally found in different residues of plants, holes in trees, ploughed soil and persistent weeds. It depicts functional activities in April. Damage causes considerable yield losses at this time (Ioan *et al.*, 1978). It furthermore attacks on chillies, tomato, tobacco, potato, onion, chrysan- themums and clover (Attique and Ahmad, 1990).

The insects are highly dependent on abiotic factors and type of crop for their proper growth and development. The population growth rate is very much during suitable environmental situations and populace abundance is too high. Temperature and relative humidity plays a role in affecting the incidence of these insect pests (Aheer *et al.*, 1994). Temperature plays a key role in controlling the development of insects and outbreaks of their population (Weisser *et al.*, 1997). The positive relationship has been found between the population of cotton thrips and environmental factors including degree of hotness, relative humidity and rainfall (Li *et al.*, 1992; Shah, 2003). For the management of thrips a latest forecasting tool was developed. It works on a specific electronic system and indicates the danger due to thrips attack (Kennedy *et al.* 2017). Keeping in view that the current study has been proposed to determine the regular outbreak of *T. tabaci* on various varieties of cotton in relation to abiotic factors and impact of different sowing dates on seasonal abundance was also intentional. This study would helpful to attain extensive information regarding to management of insect pests related to environmental and agronomic factors.

2. Materials and methods

The experiment was carried out in the trial site of CCRI (Central cotton research institute), Multan during 2018. The seasonal population dynamics of *Thrips tabaci* on two varieties of upland cotton in relation to abiotic factors was determined. Wheat and cotton were the main crops grown in that area on frequent basis. The two varieties IUB-2013 and Cyto-179 were planted in the Randomized completely block design (RCBD) with three replications on two different planting times i.e. 1st April 2018 and 1st May 2018. The size of each replicated plot was an area of 10×15 feet. The distance between plants and rows was 22.5cm and 75cm in each case respectively. An area of 3 feet was left unoccupied to avoid persuade of population of thrips on treatments (Men *et al.*, 2003). While for all the treatments agronomic practices were kept same to insure homogeneity. There was no use of pesticide during research period for efficient evaluation of study. Data as regards thrips population was recorded at weekly intervals.

Sampling Procedure

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- 1 To collect the sampling data by upper, middle and lower leaves (Prasad *et al.*, 2008)
- 2 Randomly twelve plants were selected from each replication
- 3 Zigzag method was used

Meteorological data

Accumulation of climate information to test out the effect on populace episodes of thrips: The information on ecological components (Temperature, Relative dampness and Rainfall) was taken from the physiological division of Central Cotton Research Institute (CCRI), Multan with respect to concerned days.

Statistical Analysis

The data of thrips population were analyzed by two way analysis ANOVA by using the software Statistics 8.1, while the means were separated by Tuckey's test. To check the impact of abiotic factors on thrips abundance, correlation analysis was also performed ($p=0.05$).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Thrips mean population/leaf on IUB-2013 and Cyto-179 varieties of cotton:

Seeing that the population of thrips was thought, the findings presented in table 1 point out that the thrips population was insignificant generally on both cotton varieties. While the highest number of individuals of thrips recorded from Cyto-179 (11.83/leaf) and from IUB-2013 were (8.22/leaf). The minimum thrips population found on Cyto-179 was (0.02/leaf) and IUB-2013 (0.22/leaf). On overall basis the highest outbreak of thrips populace was noted from Cyto-179 as compared to IUB-2013 (Table 1). In the present studies, as both the varieties studied were transgenic and had elevated intensity of thrips inhabitants (11.83/leaf, 8.22/leaf). The results are parallel to the findings of many other researchers in the times of yore. Like Bai *et al.* (2002), Men *et al.* (2005) and Naveen *et al.* (2007) reported the higher number of thrips on genetically modified varieties of cotton. However, in comparison Whitehouse *et al.* (2005) found lower abundance of thrips on genetically modified cotton cultivars.

Table 1: Mean populace of thrips per leaf on two distinctive cotton cultivars and two diverse sowing dates under unsprayed conditions recorded from 14th May, 2018 to 26th September, 2018 at Central Cotton Research Institute Multan (Punjab), Pakistan.

Dates	Treatments	IUB-2013	Cyto-179	Mean
14/05/2018	SD1	4.58	4.75	4.67
	SD2	2.00	2.00	2.00
21/05/2018	SD1	0.81	0.89	0.85
	SD2	0.67	0.50	0.58
28/05/2018	SD1	4.86	2.61	3.74
	SD2	0.83	0.92	0.87
04/06/2018	SD1	3.64	3.61	3.63
	SD2	1.83	1.00	1.42
11/06/2018	SD1	2.44	3.27	2.86
	SD2	0.47	0.59	0.53
19/06/2018	SD1	4.61	2.86	3.74
	SD2	1.03	0.61	0.82
26/06/2018	SD1	6.22	3.42	4.82
	SD2	1.42	1.61	1.51
03/07/2018	SD1	3.78	1.81	2.79
	SD2	2.19	1.86	2.03
10/07/2018	SD1	4.06	1.97	3.01
	SD2	3.22	3.39	3.31

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17/07/2018	SD1	0.64	0.97	0.81
	SD2	2.17	1.61	1.89
24/07/2018	SD1	0.69	0.86	0.78
	SD2	1.33	0.56	0.94
31/07/2018	SD1	0.69	0.61	0.65
	SD2	2.83	2.75	2.79
07/08/2018	SD1	3.56	4.08	3.82
	SD2	8.22	11.0	9.65
14/08/2018	SD1	6.42	7.61	7.01
	SD2	4.47	8.58	6.53
21/08/2018	SD1	6.14	4.39	5.26
	SD2	1.61	1.92	1.76
28/08/2018	SD1	0.22	0.03	0.12
	SD2	0.64	1.22	0.93
05/09/2018	SD1	3.11	3.44	3.28
	SD2	1.39	1.53	1.46
12/09/2018	SD1	0.28	0.36	0.32
	SD2	0.64	0.72	0.68
19/09/2018	SD1	0.83	0.42	0.63
	SD2	0.33	0.22	0.28
26/09/2018	SD1	0.70	0.58	0.64
	SD2	0.50	0.67	0.58

SD1= Sowing date 1, SD2= Sowing date 2

3.2 Thrips mean population on two different sowing dates:

The table (1) revealed the impact of different planting time's i.e 1st April, 2018 and 1st May, 2018 on thrips seasonal abundance. It indicates that the results were significant. The higher population pressure of thrips was found on early planted cotton. While the smaller number of thrips population was noticed from later planting date. The thrips abundance declined from earlier to later planting times (Table 1). The above findings are similar to the results of other scientists. Like Reay-Jones *et al.* (2017), Wang *et al.* (2018) reported from their studies that early planting dates had higher outbreak of thrips in comparison with later planted cotton. Parajulee *et al.* (2006) too confirmed that the abundance of thrips population was notably higher on early planted cotton in comparison with late sown cotton crop.

3.3 Thrips mean population on the combination of V×SD (Varieties × Sowing dates):

The interaction of two planting times and cultivars proved not important consequence on inhabitants fluctuation of thrips overall.

3.4 Population trend of thrips:

On tabloid base, thrips average abundance on two diverse cultivars and sowing times presented in table 1. Thrips mean abundance noted from two different planting times revealed in figure 1 and figure 2. The results revealed that in the first sown cotton, the peak activity of thrips was during the second week of August while for second planting time it was first week of August. From end of August to mid of September the thrips quantity decreased continuously on both planting times. While it starts increasing from May to mid August (Table 1). The above mentioned results are partially same like the findings of Khan and Ullah (1994), Gupta *et al.* (1997), Joginder *et al.* (1998) and Inee-Gogoi *et al.* (2000). They reported that the highest number of thrips population pragmatic through the mid of July and end of August.

3.5 Correlation analysis:

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The results from correlation analysis of abiotic factors and thrips population shown in (figures 1-8) with respect to sowing dates. The positive association observed between the thrips abundance and temperature (figure 1-2). While the analysis showed negative correlation of relative humidity (figure 3-4) and rainfall (figure 5-6) with thrips population. These findings are corresponding to the results of some other researchers. Jalal *et al.* (2006), Panickar and Patel (2001), Wahla *et al.* (1996), Ali *et al.* (1995), Khan and Ullah (1994), Al-Faisal and Kardu (1986), who also affirmed that temperature positively correlated with thrips abundance while comparative dampness and precipitation had negative association. While the *r* values for the association between population and maximum and minimum temperature were presented in (figures 7-8) respectively. The *r* value for the association between population and maximum temperature is $r=0.01$, while as the *r* value for the association between population and minimum temperature is $r=0.36$. For the successful supervision of insect pests, the compulsory thing is that one appropriately acknowledged about nature of pests and environmental aspects. Also be familiar with abiotic factors especially temperature, humidity and precipitation. These environmental factors have major position in the incidence, development and allocation of insect pests. The scientific investigations on these aspects comprised of new ways to do research. The present findings will be helpful in effective pest management program.

Figure 1: Association of average temperature (°C) to average population of thrips on two diverse cotton genotypes on first sowing date.

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Figure 2: Association of average temperature (°C) to average abundance of thrips on two diverse cotton varieties on second sowing date.

Figure 3: Association between average comparative dampness (%) and average abundance of thrips on two diverse cotton varieties on first sowing date.

Figure 4: Association between average comparative dampness (%) and average populace of thrips on two diverse cotton genotypes on second sowing date.

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Figure 5: Association between average rainfalls (mm) and average abundance of thrips on two diverse cotton genotypes on first sowing date.

Figure 6: Association between average rainfalls (mm) and average populace of thrips on two diverse cotton genotypes on second sowing date.

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Figure 7: Association between maximum temperature and population dynamics of *Thrips tabaci* on different cotton cultivars and the r value for the association between population and maximum temperature is $r=0.01$

Figure 8: Association between minimum temperature and population dynamics of *Thrips tabaci* on different cotton cultivars and the r value for the association between population and minimum temperature is $r=0.36$

4. Conclusion

The current findings showed that high abundance of thrips found on early planted cotton as compared to later planted one. While weather factors especially temperature have a positive role in development of thrips. So, by managing the agronomic factors cotton yield could be enhanced by reducing the infestation of thrips. Regarding these factors pre-planned IPM practices could be designed for effective pest management.

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